

Structure of Divalent Metal Complexes with Halide and Thiocyanate Ions in Solution

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Structural changes occurring during stepwise formation of halido and thiocyanato complexes of some divalent metal ions in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions are discussed on the basis of spectroscopic, calorimetric and solution X ray diffraction data. The structures of the complexes $[MX_n]^{2-n+}$ ($n=1-4$) are determined by the solution X-ray diffraction method and the bond-length variations due to the structural changes are shown. The step where the structure changes from octahedral to tetrahedral is shown from thermodynamic data, absorption spectra and structural analyses of the complexes. The importance of structures and properties of solvents in the complex formation reactions is especially emphasised.

Most of the solvated divalent transition-metal ions have octahedral structure, but they are tetrahedral when fully coordinated with halide and pseudo-halide ions, except for fluoride and cyanate ions. Therefore, the structural change from octahedral to tetrahedral must occur at an intermediate step of the complex formation reactions.

A number of investigations using various methods have so far been carried out for structural determinations of complexes formed in the stepwise reactions. Traditional visible spectroscopic measurements are very useful but interpretations of the spectra are not always conclusive. Certainly the method is not applicable to colourless complexes such as those of d^{10} metal ions. Nmr chemical shifts of the central metal nuclei sometimes can clearly distinguish between the octahedral and tetrahedral structures because the chemical shifts are usually largely different in complexes with different coordination structures. However, the method cannot be used for many transition metal complexes which are paramagnetic. The solution X-ray diffraction and EXAFS methods provide the direct information for the structures of metal complexes in solution, and the structural change from octahedral to tetrahedral can be directly determined by these methods. However, these methods, especially the former, need rather high concentrations of complexes in solution. When the stepwise complex formation occurs in a narrow range of concentration of a ligand so that the formation of the complexes overlaps each other, the structural determination of the individual complexes by these methods becomes rather difficult. Enthalpies and entropies of complex formation reactions also give us very important information on the structural changes of complexes, because a large gap of the enthalpy and entropy values between two complexes with different structures can be expected. However, interpretations for the changes in the thermodynamic quantities must be done very carefully because the changes contain

contributions of various energy changes accompanied by the reactions. Thus, none of the methods can be unique to determine the structure of each complex in solution, and therefore, a combination of different experimental methods is important.

Choice of solvents seems to be useful to separate stepwise reactions widely. In many nonaqueous solvents the stepwise reactions proceed more separately than in aqueous solutions. If we examine structure measurements of complexes in nonaqueous systems, the solvent effect on the complex formation reactions may be discussed from the structural point of view by knowing bond-length variations within the complexes stepwise formed. The structuredness of solvents significantly contributes to entropies of reactions. The donor-acceptor properties of solvent molecules markedly influence enthalpy values of reactions. In the present paper, thermodynamic quantities obtained for the formation of complexes are also discussed on the basis of such solvent properties and structures.

Structure of solvated metal ions :

The structure of solvated transition metal ions has already been fully discussed from visible spectra and it is well known that the first-row divalent and trivalent transition metal ions have six solvent molecules in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions. Solution X-ray diffraction measurements revealed that the fully hydrated divalent transition metal ions have six water molecules with the $M^{2+}-OH_2$ bond lengths of 220 (Mn^{2+}), 212 (Fe^{2+}), 208 (Co^{2+}), 204 (Ni^{2+}), 194 (eq) and 238 (ax) (Cu^{2+}), 208 (Zn^{2+})¹, 231 (Cd^{2+})² and 241 (Hg^{2+})³ pm. Essentially the same results have been obtained by other workers. The structures of the hydrated transition metal ions are summarised in a review by Marcus⁴. Similar structures and the M-O bond lengths have been determined for some solvated transition metal ions in O-donor nonaqueous solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO)⁵ and *N,N*-dimethylformamide

(DMF)^{5,6}. It should be noted that solvent molecules having a large molar volume cannot make the hexacoordinated structure with a divalent transition metal ion but the tetra-solvated structure is constructed. The cobalt(II) ion in hexamethylphosphoric triamide (HMPA) forms the tetra-solvated ion with the Co-O(HMPA) bond length of 194 pm⁷.

Halogeno complexes :

Copper(II) ion : Among the transition metal complexes, the copper(II)-halide complexes have been most extensively investigated for the consecutive steps of the formation reactions in aqueous and nonaqueous solvents. The colour of the solutions remarkably changes from blue of the octahedrally solvated ion to yellow of the tetrahedral tetrachloro or to brown of the tetrabromo complex.

The distorted octahedral structure of the hexa-solvated aqua and DMF complexes of the copper(II) ion has been determined by the solution X-ray diffraction method^{1,5}. The Cu-O(eq) and Cu-O(ax) bond lengths are 194 and 238 pm respectively, in water¹ and 203 and 242 pm respectively, in DMF⁵. At the complex formation the solvent molecules are stepwise replaced with halide ions.

In aqueous solution each step of formation of the complexes with halide ions is not well separated and thus the structure of the individual complexes is not determinable by the solution X-ray diffraction method without knowing concentrations of each complex in the sample solutions, which have usually high concentrations in which reliable formation constants of the complexes have hardly been evaluated. However, the structure of the individual complexes can be estimated from the shape of the visible spectra, which can be measured in dilute solutions. In nonaqueous solutions the step between each complex is often wider than that in water, and thus the structural information of the complexes can be obtained more easily.

In DMF the stepwise formation of the $[\text{CuCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ ($n=1-4$) complexes has been investigated by calorimetry^{8,9}, spectrophotometry^{8,9} and solution X-ray diffraction method¹⁰. The thermodynamic quantities obtained are summarised in Table 1. The formation constants of the complexes changed rather smoothly. However, the enthalpy of formation was largely negative and the entropy value was also negative or very small positive at the step of formation of the tetrachloro complex. The result suggests that the solvation of the $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ complex is very weak and thus the desolvation reaction of the complex may not be so endothermic that the reaction between $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ and a Cl^- ion results in the largely negative enthalpy value at this step. Desolvation of the weakly solvated chloride ion may not significantly contribute to the thermodynamic quantity. This reaction process can also explain the negative entropy value at the formation of the $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$ from $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$, because the desolvation of $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ may not largely gain entropy and the desolvated

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF CHLORO COMPLEXES OF THE COPPER(II) ION IN AN, DMF and DMSO AT 25°*

	AN	DMF		DMSO	
	0.1 M TEAP ^b [9] ^a	0.2 M TEAP ^b [8,9] ^a	1.0 M LiClO ₄ ^c [8,9] ^a	0.2 M TMAP ^b [14] ^a	1.0 M LiClO ₄ ^c [14] ^a
log K_1	9.69	6.79	3.97	4.23	3.63
log K_2	7.95	4.54	3.31	2.25	2.04
log K_3	4.94	4.00	3.45	2.47	1.83
log K_4	2.85	1.52	0.86	0.60	0.70
ΔG_1°	-55.3	-38.8	-21.6	-24.1	-20.7
ΔG_2°	-45.4	-25.9	-18.9	-12.8	-11.6
ΔG_3°	-28.2	-22.8	-19.7	-14.1	-10.4
ΔG_4°	-16.3	-8.7	-5.0	-3.4	-4.0
ΔH_1°	-11.7	10.3	1.8	9.1	3.6
ΔH_2°	-5.0	9.7	3.6	12.3	6.0
ΔH_3°	-4.4	7.3	-1.0	13.5	13.0
ΔH_4°	-34.3	-8.1	-14.3	—	-10.6
ΔS_1°	147	165	79	111	81
ΔS_2°	135	120	75	84	59
ΔS_3°	80	101	63	93	78
ΔS_4°	-61	2	-31	—	-22

*Units: K_n/M^{-1} , $\Delta G_n^\circ/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_n^\circ/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_n^\circ/\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$, $M=\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. ^aIndicates reference number. ^bTEAP=(C₂H₅)₄NClO₄. ^cIon-pair formation of LiClO₄ is not taken into account.

DMF molecules may not lose entropy very much when the molecules are involved in the bulk which has a practically random structure¹¹.

Absorption spectra of the individual complexes in DMF have been obtained by spectrophotometric measurements and the knowledge of formation constants of the complexes (Fig. 1a). The absorption spectrum of $[\text{CuCl}]^+$ has the maximum at about 260 nm or even shorter, and the shape of the spectrum is rather similar to that of the solvated ion. Therefore, the structure of $[\text{CuCl}]^+$ may be similar to that of the solvated complex which is distorted octahedral⁵. The $[\text{CuCl}_2]^0$ complex shows the absorption spectrum similar to that of $[\text{CuCl}]^+$, and thus the former may also have a distorted octahedral structure in DMF.

The structure of the $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$ complex has been discussed from the electronic spectra of copper chloride solutions^{12,13} and has been concluded to have a flattened tetrahedral structure with the D_{2d} symmetry. The electronic spectrum of $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ has a large peak at about 300 nm which coincides with the peak position of $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$, and a small peak appears at about 470 nm which may be compared with the distinct peak at 410 nm of $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$. Thus, the result suggests that $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ has a D_{2d} structure similar to that of the tetrachloro complex with one DMF molecule in the first coordination sphere of the complex.

The structures of the $[\text{CuCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes, except for $[\text{CuCl}_2]^0$, have been directly determined by the solution X-ray diffraction method¹⁰. The $[\text{CuCl}]^+$ complex has a distorted octahedral structure with five DMF molecules, and the Cu-O(eq), Cu-O(ax) and Cu-Cl(eq) bond lengths are 199, 239 and 220 pm respectively. The $[\text{CuCl}_3(\text{DMF})]^-$

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of individual $[\text{CuCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes in (a) DMF and (b) AN.

complex has a distorted (or flattened) tetrahedral structure with the Cu-O and Cu-Cl bond lengths of 230 and 219 pm, respectively. The former is longer than the latter, and thus, a remarkable elongation of the Cu-O bond has been observed. The tetrachloro complex has no solvent molecule and the Cu-Cl distance is 226 pm, which is longer than that in the $[\text{CuCl}_3(\text{DMF})]^-$ complex. From the different nonbonding Cl...Cl distances in $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$ (346 and 412 pm), the distorted tetrahedral structure of the complex is verified. Unfortunately the structure of $[\text{CuCl}_2]^0$ has not been determined by the solution X-ray diffraction method due to a low concentration of the complex, but the calorimetric and spectrophotometric data show that the complex has a distorted octahedral structure similar to the hexa-solvated and monochloro complexes.

From the experimental results, the reaction scheme is thus drawn for the complex formation reactions of the chloro complexes in DMF as follows :

Thus, the structural change occurs at the formation of the trichloro complex. The same reaction process may be occurring in DMSO¹⁴.

The electronic spectrum of $[\text{CuCl}_2]^0$ in AN is remarkably different from that in DMF and DMSO (Fig. 1b) and similar to that of $[\text{CuCl}_3]^-$ in the same solvent. Therefore, the structure of $[\text{CuCl}_2]^0$ may be distorted tetrahedral. It is expected from their donor numbers (DN) that AN (DN=14.1)¹⁵ is a weaker solvating solvent to the copper(II) ion than DMF (DN=26.6)¹⁵ and DMSO (DN=29.8)¹⁵, and therefore, the dichloro complex should be less solvated in AN than in DMF and DMSO, and the complex may be in equilibrium between the tetrahedral and octahedral structures⁹. The weaker solvation to Cu^{2+} by AN than by water (DN=18.0)¹⁵ and DMF has been shown from the enthalpies of transfer of the ion from AN to these solvents⁹. Thus the reaction scheme of the formation of the chloro complexes in AN is described as follows :

The bromo complexes of copper(II) ion in DMF behaves in a similar manner to the chloro com-

plexes in the same solvent, and it is concluded that the change from octahedral to tetrahedral occurs at the step of the formation of $[\text{CuBr}_3]^-$ in DMF¹⁶, although no X-ray diffraction measurement has been examined.

As seen from Table 1, the enthalpies of formation of the chloro complexes of copper(II) in AN are more exothermic than those in DMF and DMSO. The larger exothermicity of the reactions in AN is due to weaker solvation of AN molecules to the copper(II) ion. The smaller entropy values in DMSO than in DMF are caused by the more ordered structure of the former¹⁷ than the latter¹¹ in the bulk; the liberated solvent molecules from the coordination shell of the metal ion are involved in the bulk solvent structure with a less entropy loss in DMF than in DMSO. Rather weakly solvated AN molecules may not lose the freedom of rotational and vibrational motions in the coordination sphere of the copper(II) ion compared with DMF molecules and thus the entropy gain at liberation of solvent molecules from the coordination sphere may be less in AN than in DMF. According to solution X-ray diffraction measurements AN seems to be more structured than DMF¹⁸, which may result in, in part, the smaller entropy values in AN than in DMF (Table 1).

Zinc(II) ion: Thermodynamic quantities of the complex formation reactions between zinc(II) and chloride or bromide ions are summarised in Table 2.

It is obvious that the enthalpy values in DMF and DMSO decrease with the coordination number of the halide ions up to the formation of $[\text{ZnX}_3]^-$ (X=Cl or Br), and then the values increase at the formation of $[\text{ZnX}_4]^{2-}$ ¹⁹⁻²². On the other hand, the entropy

values are kept practically unchanged up to $[\text{ZnX}_2]^0$ in these solvents. Since the entropy values at the formation of $[\text{ZnX}]^+$ and $[\text{ZnX}_2]^0$ are largely positive in DMF and DMSO, a loss of a large number of the solvent molecules from the coordination sphere of zinc(II) is expected. The thermodynamic quantities seem to tell us that the structural change from octahedral to tetrahedral may occur at the formation of $[\text{ZnX}]^+$. A possibility of the monohalogeno complex having the pentacoordinated structure still remained, however.

Thermodynamic quantities of the complex formation reactions between zinc(II) and chloride or bromide ions in water change in more complicated ways²³ as seen in Table 2. If we extend the consideration employed to the nonaqueous solvent systems to the explanation of the thermodynamic quantities in water, the structure of the zinc(II) halogeno complexes in water might be changed between the mono- and dihalogeno complexes.

Although the donor number of water is smaller than DMF and DMSO, more water molecules can solvate the monohalogeno complex $[\text{ZnX}]^+$ than DMF and DMSO to construct the hexacoordinated complex, because the molar concentration of water is much larger (55.54 mol dm⁻³ in the pure state)

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF CHLORO AND BROMO COMPLEXES OF THE ZINC(II) ION IN WATER, DMF AND DMSO AT 25**

	$[\text{ZnCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$				$[\text{ZnBr}_n]^{(2-n)+}$		
	Water 3 M NaClO ₄ [23] ^a	DMF 0.4 M TEAP ^b [19] ^a	DMSO 0.4 M TEATFB ^c [20] ^a	DMSO 1 M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [21] ^a	Water 3 M NaClO ₄ [23] ^a	DMSO 0.1 M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [22] ^a	DMSO 1 M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [21] ^a
log K ₁	-0.19	4.81	3.5	1.94	-0.57	1.86	0.85
log K ₂	-0.40	6.99	5.1	3.90	-0.8	3.31	2.89
log K ₃	0.75	5.26	3.61	2.25	0.5	1.98	1.35
log K ₄	—	2.22	0.96	—	—	—	—
ΔG ₁ ^o	1.1	-27.5	-19.9	-11.1	3.3	-10.6	-4.8
ΔG ₂ ^o	2.4	-39.9	-29.0	-22.2	4.7	-18.9	-16.5
ΔG ₃ ^o	-4.3	-30.0	-20.6	-12.9	-3	-11.3	-7.7
ΔG ₄ ^o	—	-12.7	-5.5	—	—	—	—
ΔH ₁ ^o	5.5	14.7	16	22.3	1.5	22.3	27.8
ΔH ₂ ^o	38	1.4	8	0.8	42	19.3	9.1
ΔH ₃ ^o	0	-17.6	-11.5	-10.2	-8	-5.9	-4.2
ΔH ₄ ^o	—	-7.9	-6.7	—	—	—	—
ΔS ₁ ^o	15	142	122	112	-6	110	110
ΔS ₂ ^o	120	139	125	77	125	130	85
ΔS ₃ ^o	8	42	31	9.1	-17	18	12
ΔS ₄ ^o	—	16	-4	—	—	—	—

*Units: K_n/M^{-1} , $\Delta G_n^o/kJ \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_n^o/kJ \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_n^o/J \text{ K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $M = \text{mol dm}^{-3}$. ^aIndicates reference number.
^bTEAP = $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NClO}_4$. ^cTEATFB = $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBF}_4$.

than DMF (12.92 mol dm⁻³) and DMSO (14.03 mol dm⁻³). In fact, in highly concentrated zinc(II) chloride aqueous solutions (hydrate melts) where the contents of water in the system are very low, all of the [ZnCl_x(H₂O)_{4-x}]^{(2-x)+} (x=1-4) complexes are tetrahedral²⁴.

In solutions more than 10 mol dm⁻³ zinc(II) chloride, the tetrahedral complexes aggregate to form polymerised species. The Zn-OH₂ and Zn-Cl bond lengths are determined to be 205 and 225 pm, respectively. The Zn-OH₂ distance is shorter than that in the octahedral [Zn(H₂O)₆]²⁺ ion.

Similar experimental results have been obtained for the structures of the bromo complexes of zinc(II) ion in aqueous solutions and the Zn-Br bond length has been determined to be 238 pm in [ZnBr₂]⁰ and [ZnBr₃]⁻ and 240.5 pm in [ZnBr₄]²⁻²⁶, although unambiguous evidence for the tetrahedral structure of [ZnBr₂]⁰ and [ZnBr₃]⁻ could not be obtained in aqueous solution.

A definite conclusion on the structures of the zinc(II) halide complexes has been obtained in the aqueous zinc(II) iodide system²⁶. The structures of the complexes have been investigated by solution X-ray diffraction, Raman and far-infrared spectroscopic measurements. The structure of the [ZnI]⁺ complex is concluded to be octahedral, which changes to tetrahedral at the formation of [ZnI₂(H₂O)₂]⁰, and then tetrahedral [ZnI₃(H₂O)]⁻ and [ZnI₄]²⁻ are formed. The Zn-I bond length is 263.5 pm in [ZnI₄]²⁻ and is slightly shorter (259.2 pm) in [ZnI₂(H₂O)₂]⁰ and [ZnI₃(H₂O)]⁻. In the octahedral [ZnI(H₂O)₅]⁺ complex, the Zn-I bond length is 290 pm. The Zn-OH₂ bond lengths in the complex are approximately the same as that in the hydrated Zn²⁺ ion. Thus, the consecutive steps of the complex formation reactions between zinc(II) and halide ions in water are given as follows:

In acetic acid the zinc(II) chloro complexes are easily dimerised. The structure of the species has not been determined, but it has been postulated that the zinc(II) ions having a tetrahedral structure in the complexes are bridged by two chloride ions²⁷. The monochloro complex is supposed to be octahedral. The complexes form ion-pairs with counter cations and anions, depending on the charges of the complexes.

Cobalt(II) ion: The cobalt(II) ion is one of the most familiar ones among divalent transition metal ions which changes the colour upon complex formation with halide ions. A drastic change in colour from pink to blue occurs when an excess amount

of chloride ions is added to a cobalt(II) salt solution. Thus, spectrophotometric investigations for the colour change have been carried out to discuss the structures of the complexes formed at the consecutive steps of complex formation reactions. It is well known that cobalt(II) ion forms a hexacoordinated aqua complex in water and the tetrachloro complex is tetrahedral at room temperature. According to the spectrophotometric measurements of stepwise formation reactions between Co^{II} and Cl⁻ ions in DMF²⁸ and DMSO²⁹, the coordination structure of the cobalt(II) ion should be changed at the step of the formation of [CoCl₂]⁰. The spectra of the individual complexes in DMF are shown in Fig. 2²⁸. Similar spectra have been obtained in DMSO²⁹. Spectra of individual [CoCl_n]⁽²⁻ⁿ⁾⁺ complexes in HMPA are very similar to each other, and the result indicates that all complexes have the tetrahedral structure (Fig. 3)²⁹.

Enthalpies of formation of the complexes in HMPA are all negative, different from those in water, DMF and DMSO, and the exothermic reactions are caused by the coordination of chloride ions with the cobalt(II) ion which is weakly solvated with HMPA whose molar volume is so large that they may cause a steric hindrance between the ligands in the coordination sphere of the ion. The thermodynamic quantities of formation of the complexes in DMF²⁸, DMSO²⁹ and HMPA²⁹ as well as in water³⁰ are summarised in Table 3. It is surprising to see that few reliable works have so far been carried out for the determination of thermodynamic quantities of the complex formation reactions between Co^{II} and Cl⁻ ions in water in spite of a number of works for the complexation reactions.

The ΔH_f⁰ value is more positive than ΔH_f⁰ in DMF and in DMSO and the result suggests that more solvent molecules are liberated from the coordination shell of the metal ion at the formation of the dichloro complex in these solvents.

In HMPA, as expected from conservation of the tetrahedral structure during the reactions, no remarkable change in the ΔH_f⁰ values is observed.

In water, however, a large exothermicity and a large entropy gain have been observed at the formation of [CoCl₂]⁰ and thus it is expected that the structural change occurs at the third step of the complexation reaction. In fact, the structure of the [CoCl]⁺ complex has been determined by the solution X-ray diffraction method³¹ and the structure is octahedral with five water molecules, the Co-OH₂ and Co-Cl distances being 214 and 235 pm, respectively. The Co-OH₂ bond length thus measured was fairly long compared with the Co-OH₂ distance in the hexaaqua complex, 203 pm¹, and the elongation of the Co-OH₂ bond may be reflected to the smaller positive value of ΔH_f⁰ than ΔH_f⁰ and the essentially same value of ΔS_f⁰ as ΔS_f⁰ in water. The structure of [CoCl₄]²⁻ is tetrahedral as expected and the Co-Cl distance is

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of cobalt(II) chloride solutions in DMF. (a) Spectra with varying CX/CM ratios from 0 to 5.93. Arrows indicate the direction of the increase in the CX/CM ratio. Intensities are normalised to a unit concentration of the metal ion in solution. (b) Electronic spectra of individual $[\text{CoCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes. The number represents the n value.

TABLE 3 - THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF CHLORO COMPLEXES OF THE COBALT(II) ION IN WATER, DMF, DMSO AND HMPA AT 25°C*

	Water (27°) ^b	DMF	DMSO	HMPA
	var ^c	0.4M	0.4M	0.1M
	HCl	TEAP ^d	TEATFB ^e	TBAP ^f
	[30] ^g	[28] ^g	[20] ^g	[29] ^g
$\log K_1$	-0.8	3.76	1.6	6.7
$\log K_2$	-2.8	3.70	2.4	4.2
$\log K_3$	-2.5	4.80	3.1	2.7
$\log K_4$	-2.06	2.34	1.2	(0.8)
ΔG_1°	4.6	-21.5	-9	-38.4
ΔG_2°	16.1	-21.1	-14	-24.0
ΔG_3°	14.4	-27.4	-18	-15.5
ΔG_4°	11.8	-13.4	-6.6	(-5)
ΔH_1°	12.1	8.5	11	-15.2
ΔH_2°	8.8	27.9	30	-12.6
ΔH_3°	47.3	-2.5	7	-12.8
ΔH_4°	3.3	-6.3	-5.9	(-8)
ΔS_1°	25	101	66	78
ΔS_2°	25	164	145	38
ΔS_3°	109	84	85	9
ΔS_4°	-28	24	2	(-10)

*Units: K_n/M^{-n} , $\Delta G_n^\circ/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_n^\circ/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_n^\circ/\text{J mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$, $M=\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. ^gIndicates reference number. ^bStudied by nmr. ^cIonic strength is not constant. ^dTEAP=(C₂H₅)₄NClO₄. ^eTEATFB=(C₂H₅)₄NBF₄. ^fTBAP=(n-C₄H₉)₄NClO₄.

229 cm^{-1} . The structures of the dichloro and trichloro complexes determined by spectrophotometric measurements, have been found to be octahedral and tetrahedral, respectively^{22,23}, both being minor components in aqueous solutions. No solution X-ray data have been reported for the structure of these complexes. However, X-ray crystallographic data show that the structures of the dichloro salts with two^{24,25}, four²⁶ and six²⁶⁻²⁸ water molecules are all octahedral. The Co-OH₂ bond lengths are 204 pm in $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^{25}$, four different bond lengths 209.4, 210.7, 211.5 and 212.3 pm, in $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}^{26}$, and 208.1 pm in $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}^{26}$, while the Co-Cl bond lengths are 245.0 and 247.8 pm in $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^{25}$, 240.6 and 243.4 pm in $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}^{26}$, and 244.5 pm in $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}^{26}$. Therefore, it is expected that the dichloro complex in water is octahedral. This coincides with the conclusion derived from the thermodynamic quantities that the structural change occurs at the formation of the trichloro complex.

The tetracoordinated structures of the $[\text{CoCl}_{4-n}(\text{HMPA})_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes have been determined by the EXAFS method⁷ and the Co-O(HMPA) bond length has been determined to be 194 pm for

Fig. 3 Electronic spectra of individual $[\text{CoCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes in HMPA. The number represents the n value.

$[\text{Co}(\text{HMPA})_4]^{2+}$, $[\text{CoCl}(\text{HMPA})_3]^+$ and $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{HMPA})_2]^0$ and 202 pm for $[\text{CoCl}_3(\text{HMPA})]^-$, and the Co-Cl bond lengths are 224, 227 and 229 pm in the mono-, di- and trichloro complexes, respectively. The Co-Cl bonds in these complexes are shorter than those in the octahedral monochloro complex in other solvents, 235 pm³². The Co-Cl bond length in the tetrachloro complex in HMPA is essentially the same as that in other solvents.

Complex formation reactions between Co^{II} and Cl^- ions have also been studied in acetone⁴⁰ and acetic acid^{41,42}, in which the complexes form ion-pairs with cations or anions, depending on the charges of the complexes, of the ionic medium used. The thermodynamic quantities suggest that the monochloro complex is octahedral, while the trichloro and tetrachloro complexes are tetrahedral in acetone⁴⁰. The thermodynamic quantities and visible spectra observed in acetic acid suggest that $[\text{CoCl}]^+$ is octahedral and $[\text{CoCl}_3]^-$ and $[\text{CoCl}_4]^{2-}$ are tetrahedral⁴². The $[\text{CoCl}_2]^0$ complex exists as both tetra- and octacoordinated species which are in equilibrium and the octahedral structure is more favoured than the tetrahedral one. Therefore, the structure of the complexes changes at the second step as we have seen in other nonaqueous solvents. A similar reaction scheme to that of the chloro

complexes has been proposed for the formation of the bromo complexes in acetone⁴³ and in acetic acid⁴³.

The tetrahedral structure seems to be preserved when bromide and iodide ions coordinate to the cobalt(II) ion in HMPA, although only a part of series of the thermodynamic quantities has been determined due to weak complex formation of Co^{II} with Br^- and I^- ions⁴⁴.

From these considerations the reaction schemes for the consecutive steps of the formation of the halogeno complexes of Co^{II} in various solvents may be drawn as follows.

In water ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$):

In acetone and acetic acid ($S = \text{solvent molecule}$; $X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$):

In DMF and DMSO ($S = \text{solvent molecule}$; $X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$):

In HMPA ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$):

The concentration of solvent molecules in the solutions seems to be a factor to control the step where the octahedral structure changes to the tetrahedral one. Ligand-ligand repulsive forces due to dipole-dipole interactions may be another factor. The size of ligating atoms and solvent molecules coordinating to the central metal ions

can certainly be one of the structure-controlling factors. The electron donicity of ligand molecules may be another factor to affect the coordination structure of the central metal ion.

Nickel(II) and manganese(II) ions: Halogeno complexes of nickel(II) and manganese(II) ions are very weak in water. However, they form appreciable amounts of complexes in nonaqueous solvents. It is obvious from the spectra of nickel(II) chloride solutions in DMF¹⁹ and in DMSO²⁰ that the nickel(II) complexes change the structure at the formation of the trichloro complex (Fig. 4). Thermodynamic quantities obtained in the solvents support this conclusion because large positive values of ΔH_n° and ΔS_n° are obtained in DMF (Table 4), although sufficient thermodynamic data have not been obtained from calorimetric measurements for

the complex formation reaction of the nickel(II) ion with chloride ions in DMSO²⁰.

Nickel(II) ion prefers the octahedral structure more than the tetrahedral one compared with the cases of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} , because the former has a much larger ligand field stabilisation energy in the octahedral structure than the latter ions. The LFSE becomes the largest at Co^{2+} in the tetrahedral structure.

The ΔH_n° and ΔS_n° values of formation of the manganese(II) chloro complexes are most positive in DMF²⁸, and thus, by using an analogous consideration to that described above, we may say that the structure of the complexes changes from octahedral to tetrahedral at the formation of the dichloro complex. On the other hand, the ΔS_n° value becomes most positive and ΔH_n° seems to be slightly larger than ΔH_n° in DMSO. Therefore, it would be suggested from the variation in the thermodynamic quantities that the structural change would occur at the third step in DMSO, and this contradicts the result from the spectrophotometric study. We should be careful to discuss variations of thermodynamic quantities in connection with the structural changes when they have not a remarkable gap between steps.

Neither X-ray diffraction nor EXAFS measurements have so far been examined for the structural determination of the halogeno complexes of nickel(II) and manganese(II) ions in aqueous and nonaqueous solvents.

Cadmium(II) ion: Stepwise formation of halogeno complexes of cadmium(II) ion has mostly been investigated by potentiometry and calorimetry. Raman spectroscopy has sometimes been employed to discuss the structure of the halogeno complexes. The solution X-ray diffraction method has also been examined to determine the structure of some complexes.

In Table 5 thermodynamic quantities of stepwise formation of the halogeno complexes of cadmium(II) ion in water and in DMSO are summarised⁴⁴⁻⁵⁰. It should be noted that the formation constants of the halogeno complexes in DMSO decrease in the order, $\text{Cl}^- < \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^-$, except for K_3 (and $\text{Br}^- > \text{I}^-$ in HMPA), whereas the order is $\text{Cl}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{I}^-$ in water, which fits to a simple hard-soft concept. Desolvation of anions needs much less energy at the complex formation reactions in DMSO than in water, because the former has a much smaller acceptor number than the latter, and thus, the electrostatic interaction between cadmium(II) and halogeno ions seems to be the most important

Fig. 4. Electronic spectra of individual $[\text{NiCl}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes in DMF. The number represents the n value.

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF CHLORO COMPLEXES OF THE NICKEL(II) AND MANGANESE(II) IONS IN DMF AND DMSO AT 25°C*

	NiII		MnII	
	DMF 0.4 M TEAP ^b [19] ^a	DMSO 0.4 M TEATFB ^c [20] ^a	DMF 0.4 M TEAP ^b [28] ^a	DMSO 0.4 M TEATFB ^c [20] ^a
$\log K_1$	2.85	1.51	3.69	2.20
$\log K_2$	0.91	—	2.40	1.1
$\log K_3$	1.77	—	3.93	1.9
$\log K_4$	1.87	—	2.61	1.49
ΔG_1°	-16.3	-8.6	-21.1	-12.6
ΔG_2°	-5.2	—	-13.7	-6.3
ΔG_3°	-10.1	—	-22.4	-10.3
ΔG_4°	-10.7	—	-14.9	-8.5
ΔH_1°	8.6	9.9	1.1	62
ΔH_2°	19.1	—	25.6	23
ΔH_3°	62.9	—	5.1	26
ΔH_4°	-13.4	—	-10.5	-11
ΔS_1°	84	62	74	62.9
ΔS_2°	82	—	132	98
ΔS_3°	245	—	92	122
ΔS_4°	-9	—	15	-7

*Units: K_n/M^{-1} , $\Delta G_n^\circ/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_n^\circ/\text{kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_n^\circ/\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$, $M = \text{mol dm}^{-3}$. ^aIndicates reference number.
^bTEAP = $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NClO}_4$. ^cTEATFB = $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBF}_4$.

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF HALOGENO COMPLEXES OF CADMIUM(II) ION IN WATER, DMSO AND HMPA AT 25*

	Water 1 M NaClO ₄			DMSO 1 M NH ₄ ClO ₄			HMPA 0.1 M TBAP ^b	
	Cl ⁻ [46, 47] ^a	Br ⁻ [48, 49] ^a	I ⁻ [47, 50] ^a	Cl ⁻ [45] ^a	Br ⁻ [45] ^a	I ⁻ [45] ^a	Br ⁻ [44] ^a	I ⁻ [44] ^a
log K ₁	1.35	1.56	1.87	1.87	2.92	2.18	9.25	7.18
log K ₂	0.43	0.46	0.78	0.78	1.91	1.37	7.02	5.36
log K ₃	-0.36	0.23	1.69	1.69	2.75	2.93	4.52	2.65
log K ₄	—	0.41	1.28	1.28	1.68	1.18	1.88	—
ΔG ₁ ^o	-7.71	-8.9	-10.7	-10.7	-16.7	-12.5	-52.8	-41.0
ΔG ₂ ^o	-2.5	-2.6	-4.5	-4.5	-10.9	-7.8	-40.1	-30.6
ΔG ₃ ^o	2.1	-1.3	-9.65	-9.65	-15.7	-16.8	-25.8	-15.1
ΔG ₄ ^o	—	-2.3	-7.31	-7.31	-9.5	-6.7	-10.7	—
ΔH ₁ ^o	0.54	-4.1 ^b	-10.3	-10.3	-3.9	2.4	0.6	14.7
ΔH ₂ ^o	2.1	-2.4 ^o	-2.1	-2.1	17	27	-5.6	-4.9
ΔH ₃ ^o	7.5	7.20 ^o	-5.9	-5.9	2	-5	-18.4	-12.2
ΔH ₄ ^o	—	1.3 ^o	-16	-16	-13	-9.5	-6.4	—
ΔS ₁ ^o	28	20 ^o	1.7	1.7	43	50	179	187
ΔS ₂ ^o	15	3.3 ^o	7.9	7.9	94	117	116	86
ΔS ₃ ^o	18	42.7 ^o	13	13	59	40	25	10
ΔS ₄ ^o	—	11.3 ^o	-31	-31	-12	-10	15	—

*Units: K_n/M⁻ⁿ, ΔG_n^o/kJ mol⁻¹, ΔH_n^o/kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS_n^o/J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, M=mol dm⁻³. ^aIndicates reference number. ^bTBAP=(n-C₄H₉)₄NCIO₄. ^o3M NaClO₄.

factor for determining the K_n and ΔH_n^o values. On the other hand, the largest K_n value and the smallest ΔH_n^o values of the iodo complexes in water may be ascribed to the weakest solvation of the iodide ion in water among the three halide ions.

According to the discussion previously done for other complexes, we can say that the octahedral structure of the cadmium(II) ion changes to tetrahedral at the formation of the dihalogeno complexes in DMSO⁴⁵, because the reaction is very endothermic and the entropy of the reaction is largely positive, the fact suggesting that many solvating solvent molecules are liberated at this step. However, as similar consideration may hardly be applied to the aqueous system⁴⁶⁻⁵⁰, because the large positive values of ΔH_n^o are found at n=3 for the chloro and bromo complexes, while all the ΔH_n^o values are negative in the iodo complexes. The ΔS_n^o value becomes maximum at n=2 for all the complexes. It seems to be difficult to draw a definite conclusion for the structural change of the cadmium(II)-halogeno complexes in water. We need a further investigation for this problem.

The structure of [CdI₄]²⁻ in water has been determined by the solution X-ray diffraction method, which is tetrahedral as expected⁵¹ and the result agrees with that by Raman studies⁵¹⁻⁵⁴. The Cd-I and nonbonding I...I distances have been obtained to be 279 and 456 pm respectively⁵¹. The [CdI]⁺ complex is octahedral with the Cd-O and Cd-I bond lengths of 230 and 280 pm, respectively⁵⁵. The structure of [CdI₂]⁰ is not determinable by the solution X-ray diffraction method due to weak formation of the complex.

In DMSO the [CdI₄]²⁻ complex has the same structure as that in water with the Cd-I bond length of 279.0 pm⁵⁶. Povev *et al.*⁵⁶ determined the structure of [CdI₃]⁻ to be tetrahedral with the

Cd-O and Cd-I bond lengths of 230 and 277.3 pm, the former value having a much larger uncertainty than the latter, and the I-Cd-I bond angle of 112.4°. The structure of [CdI]⁺ has not been conclusive from their measurement⁵⁶, but the Cd-O and Cd-I bond lengths have been determined to be about 230 and 275 pm, respectively. Since the [CdI]⁺ complex is octahedral in water, we can expect that the complex may also be octahedral in DMSO. Since the thermodynamic quantities of formation of the iodo complexes of cadmium(II) ion suggest that the structural change from octahedral to tetrahedral occurs at the step of formation of [CdI₂]⁰, the reaction scheme can be drawn as follows:

In HMPA all bromo and iodo complexes of the cadmium(II) ion seem to be tetrahedral⁴⁴ and the bromo complexes are more stable than the iodo complexes. Although no investigation has been carried out for the chloro complexes, they may be much more stable than the bromo complexes. The result shows that a simple hard-soft theory is not applicable to such systems and interactions between solvent molecules and ions may play a more important role than interactions between ions in determining stabilities of the complexes in HMPA.

Mercury(II) ion: Thermodynamic quantities of halogeno complexes of the mercury(II) ion in water and DMSO are summarised in Table 6⁵⁷⁻⁶³. Stability constant of the complexes increases in

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF HALOGENO COMPLEXES OF MERCURY(II) ION IN WATER AND DMSO AT 25°*

	Water			DMSO 1 M NH ₄ ClO ₄		
	NaClO ₄ 1M Cl ⁻ [57, 58 ^b , 59 ^b] ^a	NaClO ₄ 3M Br ⁻ [60] ^a	NaClO ₄ 0.5M I ⁻ [61, 62] ^a	Cl ⁻ [63] ^a	Br ⁻ [63] ^a	I ⁻ [63] ^b
log K ₁	6.72	9.40	12.87	10.87	12.14	13.52
log K ₂	6.54	8.58	10.95	7.10	8.06	9.76
log K ₃	1.00	2.76	3.67	3.99	5.14	6.01
log K ₄	0.97	1.49	2.37	2.08	2.54	2.62
ΔG ₁ ⁰	-38.4	-53.7	-73.5	-61.0	-69.3	-77.2
ΔG ₂ ⁰	-37.3	-49.0	-62.5	-40.5	-46.0	-55.7
ΔG ₃ ⁰	-5.7	-15.8	-21.0	-22.8	-29.3	-34.3
ΔG ₄ ⁰	-5.5	-8.5	-13.5	-11.9	-14.5	-15.0
ΔH ₁ ⁰	-24.7 ^b	-40.2	-86.6	-20.3	-24.7	-33.2
ΔH ₂ ⁰	-28.9 ^b	-40.2	-77.7	-28.5	-31.9	-39.4
ΔH ₃ ⁰	-9.2 ^b	-10.9	—	-20.1	-27.8	-28.1
ΔH ₄ ⁰	-0.4 ^b	-18.4	—	-14.0	-19.1	-21.1
ΔS ₁ ⁰	46.4 ^b	45.6	-7.2	140	149	148
ΔS ₂ ⁰	2 ^b	30	-20	40	47	54
ΔS ₃ ⁰	-13 ^b	17	—	9	5	21
ΔS ₄ ⁰	21 ^b	-34	—	-7	-16	-21

*Units: K_n/M^{-1} , $\Delta G_n^0/kJ\ mol^{-1}$, $\Delta H_n^0/kJ\ mol^{-1}$, $\Delta S_n^0/J\ K^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$, $M = mol\ dm^{-3}$. ^aIndicates reference number. ^b0.5 M HClO₄.

the order, $Cl^- < Br^- < I^-$ as expected from the simple hard-soft concept. The enthalpy of the reactions changes in the same order as the stability constants. The stability constants and entropies largely change at the formation of $[HgX_3]^-$ ($X=Cl, Br$ and I) in water⁵⁷⁻⁶³ but no drastic change of ΔH_n^0 is observed in DMSO⁶³. The reaction is most exothermic at the formation of $[HgCl_4]^0$ in water and all dihalogeno complexes in DMSO, but the minimum ΔH_n^0 value appears at the formation of $[HgI]^+$ and $\Delta H_1^0 = \Delta H_2^0$ for the bromo complexes in water.

According to the solution X-ray diffraction measurements in DMSO and DMF, $[HgI_2]^0$ has the almost linear I-Hg-I structure with the Hg-I bond length of 260 pm and loosely bound DMSO or DMF molecules⁶⁴. Since the I-Hg-I bond is linear and it combines with some solvent molecules, it probably has a hexacoordinated structure with the two iodo ions at the *trans*-position. The $[HgI_2]^-$ complex has a tetrahedral structure with the Hg-I bond length of 273 pm⁶⁴. The pyramidal $[HgI_3]$ moiety is slightly flattened and the height of the mercury atom over the base plane is smaller than that expected from the value of the regular tetrahedron. The tetraiodo complex is tetrahedral in DMSO and DMF and the Hg-I bond length is 280 pm. Essentially the same result has been obtained in water⁶⁵.

Although the structure of $[HgI]^+$ has not directly been determined by means of solution X-ray diffraction, it is expected to have an octahedral structure, because the solvated Hg^{2+} ion in water, DMSO and DMF is octahedral and $[HgI_2]^0$ is also octahedral. The changes in the thermodynamic quantities shown in Table 6 should, therefore, be

explained in terms of weakening of the metal-solvent bonds during the consecutive steps of the complex formation reactions.

Similar results to those found for the iodo complexes have been obtained for the structures of the bromo complexes in water. The Hg-Br bond length is 261.0 pm for the tetrabromo complex and the bond is slightly longer by about 3 pm than that in the tribromo complex in water⁶⁵.

Mercury(II) chloride polymerises in water at high concentrations⁶⁶. The Hg-Cl bond length in the tetrahedral $[HgCl_4]^{2-}$ complex is 247 pm. No X-ray diffraction study has been carried out for the other mononuclear complexes.

The scheme of the consecutive steps of formation of the halogeno complexes, except for the chloro complexes of the mercury(II) ion may be represented as follows:

The different schemes in the Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} systems may be ascribed to different ionic sizes between the ions.

Thiocyanato complexes:

Zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) ions: Thermodynamic quantities of formation of the thiocyanato complexes of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) ions in water, DMF and DMSO are

TABLE 7—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES OF STEPWISE FORMATION OF THIOCYANATO COMPLEXES OF ZINC(II), CADMIUM(II) AND MERCURY(II) IONS IN WATER, DMF AND DMSO AT 25°*

	Zn ^{II}			Cd ^{II}			Hg ^{II}		
	H ₂ O 1M NaClO ₄ [67] ^a	H ₂ O 5M NaClO ₄ [63] ^a	DMSO 1M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [21] ^a	H ₂ O 3M NaClO ₄ [69] ^a	DMF 0.4M TEAP ^b [70] ^a	DMF 1M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [70] ^a	DMSO 1M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [45] ^a	H ₂ O 1M NaClO ₄ [67] ^a	DMSO 1M NH ₄ ClO ₄ [63, 71] ^a
log β _{1,1}	—	—	—	1.25	—	—	—	—	—
log K ₁	0.71	0.917	1.88	1.378	3.57	2.77	1.81	9.08	9.33
log K ₂	0.34	0.673	1.40	0.396	2.41	1.84	0.91	7.78	5.66
log K ₃	0.15	0.577	2.43	0.052	1.61	1.08	0.20	2.84	2.66
log K ₄	0.32	0.347	1.65	0.180	1.23	0.86	—	1.97	2.31
ΔG ₁ ⁰	—	—	—	-7.14	—	—	—	—	—
ΔG ₂ ⁰	-4.1	-5.2	7.9	-7.9	-20.4	-15.8	-10.3	-51.8	-53.3
ΔG ₃ ⁰	-2	-3.8	-8.0	-2.2	-13.8	-10.5	-5.2	-44.4	-32.3
ΔG ₄ ⁰	-1	-3.3	-13.9	-0.3	-9.2	-6.2	-1.1	-16.2	-16.9
ΔG ₅ ⁰	-2	-2.0	-9.4	-1.0	-7.0	-4.9	—	-11.2	-13.2
ΔH ₁ ⁰	—	—	—	-14.8	—	—	—	—	—
ΔH ₂ ⁰	-5.8	-5.0	5.5	-10.2	-4.9	-5.8	-3.0	-49.7	-28.1
ΔH ₃ ⁰	-2	2.9	23.5	-20.1	-4.3	-5.9	-2.8	-50.4	-31.1
ΔH ₄ ⁰	-1	-6.3	-17.8	22.6	1.9	0.5	4.2	-20.4	-8.7
ΔH ₅ ⁰	-8	-4.4	-10.7	-22.8	9.9	8.9	—	-21.0	-16.8
ΔS ₁ ⁰	—	—	—	-25.7	—	—	—	—	—
ΔS ₂ ⁰	-6	1	45	-8	52	33	25	7	85
ΔS ₃ ⁰	0	23	105	-60	32	16	8	-20	4
ΔS ₄ ⁰	0	-10	-13	77	37	22	18	-14	24
ΔS ₅ ⁰	-20	-14.4	-4	-73	56	-6	—	-33	-12

*β_{1,1}=[Cd₂SCN²⁺]/([Cd²⁺][SCN⁻]); units: K_n/M⁻ⁿ, β_{1,1}/M⁻², ΔG_n⁰/kJ mol⁻¹, ΔH_n⁰/kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS_n⁰/K⁻¹ mol⁻¹; ΔG_n⁰, ΔH_n⁰, and ΔS_n⁰ are the corresponding values of the overall formation reaction of [Cd_nSCN]²⁺, M=mol dm⁻³.
^aIndicates reference number. ^bTEAP=(C₂H₅)₄NClO₄.

summarised in Table 7^{21,45,63,67-71}. Besides the mononuclear complexes, a dinuclear [Cd₂SCN]³⁺ complex has been found in an aqueous cadmium(II) thiocyanate solution containing 3M (M=mol dm⁻³) NaClO₄ as an ionic medium in which the concentration of the cadmium(II) ion can be higher than that in solutions of low ionic strengths.

In the zinc(II) system, ΔH₂⁰ is a positive or a very small negative value^{6,9}, which suggests that the structure of the octahedrally solvated zinc(II) ion in water and in DMSO probably changes to the tetrahedral structure at this stage, because the final product, the tetrathiocyanatozincate(II) complex, is tetrahedral⁷². The ΔS₂⁰ value is largely positive which supports the structural change. On the other hand, in the cadmium(II) system, the maximum values of ΔH_n⁰ and ΔS_n⁰ appear at n=3 in water, and thus the octahedral dithiocyanatocadmium(II) complexes may turn to the tetrahedral trithiocyanatocadmium(II) complex upon the addition of a thiocyanate ion in the coordination shell. Changes in ΔG_n⁰ and ΔH_n⁰ in water in the cases of the mercury(II) system are not very drastic compared with those in the other two cases, although a positive value has been observed for ΔS₁⁰. Explanations of the changes in the thermodynamic quantities do not seem to be simple in DMF and DMSO.

Solution X-ray diffraction measurements on aqueous solutions containing the tetrathiocyanato complexes of zinc(II) and mercury(II) ions showed that the complexes have the tetrahedral structure with the Zn-N and Hg-S bonds respectively⁷².

However, the solution X-ray diffraction measurements for the tetrathiocyanatocadmium(II) ion in the aqueous solution revealed that the complex has two Cd-N and two Cd-S bonds (Fig. 5)⁷². Raman spectra of the solutions indicated that the tetrathiocyanatozincate(II) and -mercurate(II) complexes have only Zn-N (the C-S stretching frequency ν_{C-S} appears at 821 cm⁻¹) and Hg-S bonds (ν_{C-S}=710 cm⁻¹), respectively, while the Raman spectrum of the tetrathiocyanatocadmium(II) complex shows the frequencies arising from the C-S bond with both Cd-N and Cd-S bondings (ν_{C-S}=779 and 732 cm)⁷².

The bond lengths between the metal ions and the ligand atoms are depicted, together with the bond angles, in Fig. 6. It should be noted that the Cd-S distance is close to the sum of the ionic radii of each ion and longer than the length of the Hg-S bond which is better explained in terms of the covalent bonding than the ionic bonding.

Thus a question arises how the consecutive steps of interactions between cadmium(II) and thiocyanate ions proceed to the final product of [Cd(NCS)₄]²⁻ (SCN)₂²⁻. In Fig. 7, Raman spectra of cadmium(II) thiocyanate solutions with varying C_X/C_M ratios (C=molar concentration, X=SCN⁻, M=Cd²⁺). The main species produced in the solutions at given C_X/C_M values are indicated in the figure. Around C_X/C_M=0.6, the dinuclear [Cd₂X]²⁺ is formed, and at about 1.0-1.7, [CdX]⁺ is dominant. In a solution of the highest C_X/C_M value in the figure, the dithiocyanato complex becomes the main species. As it has already been mentioned, the C-S stretching frequency in the SCN⁻ ion shifts

Fig. 5. Difference radial distribution curves of aqueous thiocyanate solutions of (a) zinc(II), (b) cadmium(II) and (c) mercury(II) ions. The upper curves show the theoretical peak shapes of each atom-pair and the lower ones show the difference radial distribution curves (thick lines) and the residual curves (dotted lines) after subtraction of the theoretical peak shapes from the radial distribution curves

towards the lower and higher frequency sides when the sulphur and nitrogen atoms, respectively, bind with the metal ion ($\nu_{C-S} = 747 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in free SCN^-). In the spectrum of a solution at $C_X/C_M = 0.649$ where the dinuclear $[\text{Cd}_2\text{X}]^{2+}$ complex is formed, three bands appeared at about 720, 760 and 780 cm^{-1} , the second one could be ascribed to the band of the free SCN^- ions, while the first and third ones could be attributed from the C-S bond with

Cd-S and Cd-N bondings respectively, in the complex. It is thus obvious that the dinuclear complex has the Cd-N and Cd-S bonds.

The band at about 780 cm^{-1} increased the height with an increase in the C_X/C_M value and then decreased at high C_X/C_M . Therefore, we can conclude that mononuclear $[\text{CdX}]^+$ complex has the Cd-N bond. The 720 cm^{-1} band still remained in the

Fig. 6. The bond lengths and bond angles in the tetra-thiocyanato complexes of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) formed in water. The unit of the length is in pm.

Fig. 7. Raman spectra of cadmium(II) thiocyanate aqueous solutions with varying C_X/C_M ratios.

solutions of $C_X/C_M = 1.27 - 1.65$ where the dinuclear complex could no more exist and the dithiocyanato complex began to form. Therefore, the result suggested that the dithiocyanato complex has the Cd-S bond. A new band around 740 cm^{-1} appearing in the excess SCN^- ions in the solution (Fig. 7). Thus, the $[\text{CdX}_2]^0$ complex might have both Cd-N and Cd-S bonds and it should be described as $[\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})(\text{SCN})]^0$.

Raman spectroscopic measurements in the C-N frequency region of the SCN^- ion gave similar results, although the conclusion derived from the

frequency shifts of the C-N band is not so clear compared with the observations of the C-S frequencies, since the C-N frequency shifts towards the same direction of the lower frequency side of the C-N band of free ions at the formation of the metal-N and metal-S bonds.

When we look at the thermodynamic data of the stepwise formation reactions of the $[\text{CdX}_n]^{(2-n)+}$ complexes in Table 7, we see very similar values of ΔH_4^0 to ΔH_2^0 and of ΔS_4^0 to ΔS_2^0 , the result suggesting that the Cd-S bond formation occurs at the fourth step as the bond forms at the second step. If the Cd-S bond forms at the second and fourth steps, the Cd-N bond must be formed at the formation of $[\text{CdX}_3]^-$ from $[\text{CdX}_2]^0$.

From these considerations described above, the reaction schemes of the thiocyanato complexes of the zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) ions in water may be given as follows :

The same reaction schemes given above may be written for the formation of the thiocyanato complexes of zinc(II) and mercury(II) ions in DMF, because the thermodynamic quantities of the complex formation reactions of Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} with SCN^- change in similar manners to those in water. Consecutive steps of formation of $[\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_n]^{(2-n)+}$ in DMSO^{7,8} seem to take the same manner as those in water and in DMF. However, the reaction scheme for the complex formation reactions of Cd^{II} with SCN^- in DMF is different from that in water, because the final product of $[\text{CdX}_4]^{2-}$ in DMF has a different structure from that in water.

A solution X-ray diffraction measurement for the tetrathiocyanatocadmiate(II) complex has been carried out in a DMF solution containing $\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2$ and NH_4SCN ^{7,4}. The radial distribution curve experimentally obtained and the theoretical peak shapes calculated from the data of intermolecular

interactions in the system are shown in Fig. 8. It is obvious from the figure that the peak of the Cd-S interaction is relatively small compared with that in the aqueous solution (Figs. 5d and 8b), and the result indicates that a less number of Cd-S bonds exist in the $[\text{CdX}_4]^{2-}$ complex in DMF than in water. From the analysis of the

Fig. 8. The difference radial distribution curve of a cadmium(II) thiocyanate solution in DMF containing an excess amount of NH_4SCN . (a) The theoretical peak shapes of atom-pairs in NH_4^+ and SCN^- ions and in DMF molecule. (b) The theoretical peak shapes in the tetrathiocyanatocadmium(II) ion. (c) The difference radial distribution curve of the solution (solid line), the residual curve after subtraction of peak shapes in (a) from the solid line (chain line), and the residual curve after subtraction of peak shapes in (b) from the chain line (dotted line).

radial distribution curve of the solution, we have found that the tetrathiocyanatocadmium(II) complex has the structure of $[\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_3(\text{SCN})]^{2-}$. The structures and the bond lengths in the complexes are shown in Fig. 9.

The difference in the coordination structures of the tetrathiocyanatocadmium(II) complex in water and in DMF may be ascribed to different solvation

in water

in DMF

Fig. 9. The structure of the tetrathiocyanatocadmium(II) complex in water and in DMF.

tendencies of the thiocyanate ion in the two solvents. The thiocyanate ion prefers to be solvated

with water molecules at the N-site. The solvation of the ion becomes much weaker in aprotic DMF with a smaller acceptor number than water, and solvation at the N-site may be especially weakened and consequently solvation at the S-site may become even relatively stronger than that at the N-site^{7,8}. Therefore, formation of the Cd-N bond may become more favourable in DMF than in water, and thus, the $[\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{SCN})]^{2-}$ structure may be constructed in DMF. The coordination geometry of the $[\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{SCN})]^{2-}$ complex may be favourable rather than that of $[\text{Cd}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{SCN})_2]^{2-}$ in the respect of solvation of the complex itself in DMF, because the former structure exposes more S atoms of ligating SCN^- ions into the bulk DMF which can probably better solvate the S atoms than the N atoms in the ligands.

Concluding remarks :

It is a rather common phenomenon that the coordination geometry changes in the course of the stepwise complex formation reactions between a metal ion and a kind of ligands. However, few investigations have so far been carried out to elucidate the full process of the reactions. In this paper we showed some examples in which the full schemes of the consecutive steps of the complex formation reactions could be described from thermodynamic, spectroscopic and solution X-ray diffraction studies. Interestingly the reaction schemes are sometimes strongly influenced by solvents. Therefore, the structure and properties of solvents must be well understood in interpretations of complex formation reactions in solution.

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